

Effective Communication as a Tool for Achieving Organizational Goals and Objectives

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ABSTRACT: Communication is a critical element of human behavior. In other words, it's an act by which one person gives to or receives information from another person that involves a person's needs, desire, knowledge, opinions, and perceptions. Communication within the workplace can occur under various modes like writing, verbal and nonverbal (body gestures and facial expression). In business and industry, communication helps align workers with figuring out each other and realizing the target of the organization, which suggests objectives, are often within the target, attained, and improved. Without workplace communication, nothing can be done. Keyton's study found that communication can be defined as a procedure of transmitting information from one person to another person and understand it. It is also known as an instrument of social relations. It helps people understand themselves to keep in touch with people and predict their response to a situation. This paper explores the role that communication plays to achieve an organization or business' goals and objectives.

KEYWORDS: Effective Communication, Workplace, Business Goals, Barriers to Effective Communication and Verbal and Nonverbal Communication.

I. INTRODUCTION

Researches have shown that any self-sustainable system must secure, enhance and preserve effective communication among its components or agents and their coordination and self-coordination competence. Hence, communication is a crucial tool in any human organization. Be it social, business, religious, political, etc., the sole vital tool employed in conveying helpful information is thru communication. It's a universal truth that man uses a good percentage of his daily activities communicating with his environment.

According to Richter (2000), communication is a method of meaningful interaction among the citizenry. It's the act of passing information and, therefore, how meanings are exchanged to produce understanding. Communication may be a process that needs a sender, a message, a medium, and a recipient. Though the receiver might not be involved or conscious of the sender's intent to speak at the time of communication, it's expedient that the communicating parties share an area of communicative commonality. Thus, communication can take place across vast distances in both time and space. According to Daramola (1997), communication is ubiquitous. It takes place everywhere, every day, and every time. It is all around us. As a result, we all engage in communication with each other at the reception, within the office, school, and industry.

Organizations everywhere around the world are either adjudged to be high, medium, or low flyers, counting on how they relate with their operational environment in terms of social responsibilities, tasks, and service delivery to clients and employees alike.

How successfully a corporation achieves its objectives, satisfies social responsibilities, or both depends on its managers' communication skills. If managers communicate well, the organization will probably reach its goals, and the state will work properly. Today, there's increasing concern and debate, analysis, and confusion around the world over how managers do their jobs – managerial performance – because it is with organizational performance – a measure of how well organizations can do their job. Thus, effective communication is essential for the continued corporate existence of each organization.

Good communication is a significant aspect of effective coordination of its resources (human and non-human) into efficient and desirable teams. The adversity of effective communication to executives or managers of organizations stems, particularly from two reasons. First, communication is the process by which managers accomplish the functions of designing, organizing, leading, and controlling. Second, communication is an activity to which managers devote a remarkable proportion of their time. Very less

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often, we see managers aloof at their desks pondering, planning, or thinking about alternatives. A manager's time is spent chiefly in face-to-face, electronic or telephonic communication with subordinates, supervisors, and suppliers. When not conferring with others face to face or on the phone, they'll be writing, dictating memorandums, letters, or reports or reading memos, letters, or information sent to them. Precisely why Lukaszewski (2006) pointed that; "The greatest continuing area of weakness in management practice is the human dimension. In good and bad times, there is a very little understanding of the relationship between managers, among employees, and interactions between both parties. When there are problems, everyone acknowledges that the cause often may be a communication problem. So now what?"

II. BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

Communication touches every sphere of human activity. It informs or, better still, disseminates information/message to the target audience. One of the peculiarities of the human race is communication among the members of society. Communication is an essential attribute of human behavior. Indeed, communication is perhaps man's most crucial singular activity because every other human activity revolves around communication.

Animals and trees also communicate, but man can create a symbol, ascribe meanings, and interpret messages that elevate him above the lower animals' status and gives form and character to his existence. All organizations encourage effective communication by establishing channels (formal and informal) for transmitting information to people. An influential organization channel must send company policies, programs, rules, and regulations to all enterprises. It is also necessary for dealing with customers, regulatory agencies, and the general public. Through good communication with business owners, board of directors, management, peers, and subordinates, an organization maintains goodwill, grows, and waxes.

Communication serves as a tool for social interrelation. It helps us understand ourselves, keep in touch with other people, understand them, and predict their response to the situation, its means by which power is acquired, exercised, and sustained. It is the medium through which relationships are built and nurtured for lifetimes. It provides a means by which people in business policies make decisions and management and materials. In business and industry, communication helps to orient workers to work with one another and achieve the organization's reasonable goals. It is how such goals can be pursued, attained, sustained, and improved.

It is the lubricant that keeps the machinery of an organization functioning. It's a means to identify and assign roles and is the lifeblood of an organization. The above brief historical consideration of communication emphasizes its importance in human existence. To organize is to communicate; thus, the survival of an organization is impossible without communication. The effect of marketing communication in an organization can be measured in terms of attitude and performance, for it affects the employees' morale and their attitude towards organizational productivity. Communication is the act of transferring information from one person to another; it could also transmit and convey ideas, attitudes, views, and opinions from person to person, generation to generation, or a vast audience, and vice versa.

Social organizations cannot survive without communication. Imagine what the situation will be like if you gather people together and not communicate with them; the problem will be pretty uncontrollable. No matter how poor or rich an organization is, there exists some spectrum of communication. It is crucial for the success of an organization. Communication is indispensable to human existence because one must communicate with people around him to share ideas, experiences, and feelings. An organization must have working channels of communication and keep working on the ones already existing. Employers should help the employees, customers, and the general public communicate to help streamline action and activities within the organization. The employees, more especially, would like to know the organization's objectives for which they are working. They will affect them are about to be effective. They will also like to know what is expected of them in the organization, to abide by the rules and regulations sent to make known to the organization about their feelings, decisive, aspiration, and efforts. They will also like to be recognized by other members of the organization, especially management. An organization is deemed a good one when its objectives are derived from its members. This can only be achieved by establishing an effective communication strategy. Hence it is well informed of the organizational plans and given at the same time the chance to make its contributions to the advantage of the management and its entity.

Every organization has a goal that it strives to achieve and live up to. For instance, at their various levels, legal institutions aim to turn out good, disciplined, and well-behaved citizens for the country's social, economic, and political development. Police and other law enforcement agencies have the objective of curbing and suspension of deviant behaviors and bringing order to sanity.

A. The Society

Business organizations are set up to provide goods and services to the people at minimum cost and minimum profit. At their various levels, educational institutions aim to turn out literate citizens with a high-level workforce for their social, economic, and

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political development, voluntary and religious organizations. Examples include; the red – cross boys – scouts, girls guides, boys brigades, and girls brigades. Various churches are set up as mortal instruments for character molding that offer humanitarian services to the needy.

According to Ukeku (1983: 20), human resources are essential tools of every organization since without them, other resources cannot operate.

These personnel, who are the vehicles through which organizational objectives are attained, have to be appropriately managed for effective performance. Aenyer (1970:20) is concerned with the direction and control of an organization; it involves planning and supervision of others' work.

These managerial functions can't be successfully executed in the absence of communication. It is imperative in the role of directing and leading. It is only when people can open up and burst each other with their true selves. Hence, we can call communication as the life wire of an organization.

B. Communication Function

It is how an organizational activity is unified, social inputs are fed into, behavior is modified, information is made productive, and goals are achieved. A personnel officer or a superior officer engages in communication with an individual to change his behavior. He may have the discipline or corrective objective in a counseling situation with emotional content; the superior should listen empathically to the subordinates. Empathy means putting oneself in somebody else's shoes or place and emotions. Therefore, empathetic listening is part of two-way communication. The associate must have the opportunity to express himself, and it is only when he has made himself know that the superior will know where to assist him.

Communication is essential for both the internal and external functioning of enterprises. It's needed internally, including integrating the management function to development plans for their achievement to organize human and material resources for maximum productivity and create a conducive atmosphere for effective and efficient organizational performance. External communication is also vital for every organization to achieve success. Through information exchange, managers know the needs of their numerous customers, both consumers and suppliers, legal and community requirements, conditions in the labor market, new product line expectations, plans, and strengthen programs for business trend innovations.

No organization, be it military, business, religious, and even government, can succeed without external interaction and influence, which is only possible through communication.

Brow (1985:116) stressed that communication is the process of transmitting ideas and thoughts from one person to another to create ideas and thoughts from one person to another to create understanding in the person's thinking.

This emphasis on understanding brings attention to the significance of communication for effective organizational performance. Anker (1978:102) stated that information is the manager's primary tool since; he does not "handle" people but motivates, guides and directs them to conform to the desired goals. The manager's only means to do this language charts gestures and other movements.

Whatever method is applied, the important thing is understanding by the receiver for the necessary action no matter the manager's job; his effectiveness depends on his ability to speak and to write clear enough to get his thinking across to other people and understand what other people are after. Managers should aim to organize and coordinate their organization's human and material resources into an effective and efficient working unit. To achieve this, he must spend a few hours from his day on learning communication. Only when an organization's human and material elements are harnessed into a united whole can the organization's objective be achieved through effective performance.

Despite the importance of communication for effective organizational performance, many business organizations in Nigeria today pay no attention to it. In the office, most files are labeled confidential, the result being, those who are supposed to utilize the information for adequate performance are denied access to the fact. How can an organization MEMBER PERFORM CREDITABLE WELL WHEN HE IS NOT? When can an organization's member know when he is contravening the rules and regulations in his organization when on-one has cared to make such information known to him? How can such an organization expect to succeed or achieve its objective when with whom and through whom it wished to achieve its goals are not aware of "while" indolence, strikes, and sick reports are abound in the public office. Strikes and the likes occur more frequently due to poor and ineffective communication between the management and members of the organization. In no way does this aid the organization in its efforts to achieve its objectives. Given this, the research hopes that this will help direct the readers' minds towards realizing the importance of effective communication in an organization. It is true that effective communication minimizes misunderstanding and increases mutual understanding, trust, and selfless services among organization employees.

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III. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Today, most business organizations have failed to satisfy their potential customers not in quality or quantity of such goods and services provided but in creating adequate awareness and enlightenment to its customers.

Before a product is made available for its market, organizations should determine how to communicate it to potential customers. The task involves the use of effective communication between the marketing firm and its target audience. Through communication, marketers can inform the target audience about their product, price, and performance, where they may purchase it from, etc.

In communicating a product, marketers are faced with both controllable and uncontrollable problems such as the product, price, promotion, competitors, the economy of the nation, etc. To solve these problems, an organization should put up a communication message that will attract attention, hold interest, arouse desire, and elicit action by choosing the most efficient means of getting their message across to their target audience or potential customers.

One of the problems being faced today is that organizations want to keep talented employees in the organization but don't know how to ensure their stay. We usually hear several reasons why employees leave the organization, including being offered higher pay, getting more benefits, career development, etc. But, according to McConnell's study, these adverse effects include loss of productivity from position vacancy, inefficiency associated with the coworkers of the leaving individual taking responsibility for their duties on top of their own, further inefficiency of the incoming employee during training and orientation to the new position and costs associated with human resource processing.

Effective communication among employees in the organization is related to communication mode to develop an understanding of strategies that foster quality communication, impacting any organization's success. According to employers and employees must be consistent, clear, complete, and accurate when communicating with each other. Some of the barriers may include body gestures, language, culture, emotions, and personalities when communication breakdowns occur.

A. The Need for Effective Communication in an Organization

Effective communication is a critical tool for organizational success. For an organization's management to perform its essential functions of organizing, directing, coordinating, etc., it must apply a system or means of communication that is very effective. A Management Study Guide states that Effective communication is a building block to a successful organization". In other words, communication acts as organizational blood. Madlock (2008) noted that "if planned strategically, internal communication will significantly enable the organization to achieve its goals more effectively." Effective communication in an organization can help managers perform their jobs and responsibilities very well and in a coordinated manner.

B. Barriers to Communication in Organizations

There is no doubt that communication is essential for the effective and efficient management of every organization. Yet, managers/chief executives have found communication very problematic and stressful because of specific barriers.

These communication barriers include communication overload, wrong expressed messages, inappropriate medium, poor listening, premature evaluation, grapevine, hostility between the participants, bureaucracy, social distance, communication filtering, and distractions by personal and family problems. Diwan (2000) reasoned that "the problem of effective communication is unfortunately greater than just the recognition of its scale and importance." As it were, effective communication is required for productivity in any organization. To this end, Koontz (2001), while highlighting barriers to effective communication in an organization, opined that communication problems are often symptoms of more deep-rooted challenges, such as poor planning may be the reason behind uncertainty about the goals or direction of the organization.

Succinctly, some barriers to effective communication, as highlighted in Onuoha (1991), include communication overload, poorly expressed message, inappropriate medium/Language, poor listening/decode, and premature evaluation arising from lack of understanding, hostility between the participants, bureaucracy, and grapevine with informal organizations within organizations.

IV. THE SOLUTION

A. Overcoming Barriers to Communication in Organizations

To deal with communication barriers in organizations, managers must first recognize that communication is an inherently complex process. Communication is intrinsically difficult because human beings perceive and interpret reality according to their backgrounds, needs, emotions, values, and experiences. A production manager's memorandum to a supervisor asking for a figure on absenteeism will be seen as a legitimate request by one supervisor and as unnecessary meddling by another supervisor. A manager's instruction may seem coldly formal to some subordinates and polite to others. A quarterly report may seem clear to one superior and confusing to another. Some writers believe that most organizational barriers to communication are based on how people interpret the communication they receive. Often, these can be traced to cultural

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differences. In a nutshell, an efficient organization depends on the effectiveness of internal communication. And with the presence of communication barriers, how can an organization improve its communication networks. American Management Association suggests some useful steps in this direction. These include:

1. Clarity of ideas before attempting to communicate.
2. Examining the purpose of communication.
3. Understanding the physical and human environment when communicating.
4. While planning communication, consult with others to obtain their support as well as the facts.
5. Consider the content and overtone of the message.
6. Try to communicate something that helps or is valued by the receiver.
7. Communication to be effective needs or require follow-up.
8. Communicate messages that are short-run and long-run importance.
9. Actions must be congruent with communication.
10. Be a good listener.

Communication is a crucial component used to meet organizational goals and objectives. Stimulation and motivation of employees via organizational communication is the pillar behind successful achievement of these goals. Communicating may be non-verbal or verbal. Non-verbal communication is important to successful workplace relationships through body movement, including gestures, posture and gait, and facial expression. Nonverbal communication is also associated with social behavior and can be viewed as a conveyor of emotion. 65% to 75% of most communication is nonverbal and includes cues about what we sense, feel and think about others. Breakdown in the communication will occur because of the misinterpretation of information received. Wrong word choice, differing communication styles, and perspectives can all contribute to communication breakdown. In general, communication climate can be defined as the internal environment of information exchange between employees through formal and informal networks. The communication climate is open when information flows freely and closes when information is completed. Thus, a negative communication climate is created when individuals contribute to the organization but are not appreciated. A negative climate makes it difficult for employees to get and give information and to take action. Employees feel uncomfortable and unwilling to interact with each other.

Next, the supervisor is a front-line management person who monitors an employee's performance when assigned. They are usually authorized in hiring, disciplining, promoting, punishing, rewarding, and any employment activities in the departments. Besides, the supervisor can offer rewards or punish employees. Furthermore, the supervisor must be able to communicate effectively in terms of transferring knowledge and motivation. The research shows that supervisor's listening skills were perceived as crucial in assessing the effectiveness of supervisory communications. Moreover, there is a theory that Sullivan's Motivating Language Theory (MLT) hypothesizes that superior's use as motivating language, giving direction or sharing feelings, and explaining cultures will positively impact employee performance and job satisfaction. In the US, it has been proved by Sullivan's MLT that strategic applications of leader oral communication have positive, measurable effects on subordinate performance and job satisfaction.

Moreover, the Contemporary economy is changing rapidly. It is characterized by globalization and deregulation of markets, changing customer demands, and increasing competition. Every organization has a specific objective that they target to achieve to manage all kinds of problems. That's why objective becomes vital towards organizational success.

Figure 2.1 shows the theoretical framework for the dimension of communication satisfaction.

Figure 2.1: Framework of dimension of communication satisfaction

V. COMMUNICATION AND STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT DEFINED

Communication is defined and explained in multiple ways by intellectuals of various interests and disciplines in management, psychology, and sociology. Communication pervades across every aspect of life, including business, domestic, and social interactions. Anugwom (2007) defines communication as using words, signs, and symbols to interchange ideas, emotions, facts, and information by two or more persons. Nwokeneme (2008) defined communication as a process that comprises the

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transmission of message or information through a channel from sender to receiver. From a wider perspective, communication is a process by which information is passed between individuals and organizations using previously agreed symbols. Inyang and Esu (2003) define communication as the process of transmitting meaning from sender to receiver. Other scholars such as Dessler (2004:94-110), Adams (2006; 16-24), and Smith (2008:42-51) have agreed that communication is simply a transmission or exchange of meaning.

According to Image (2003:75), strategic management means a mindful approach to organizing, staffing, directing, leading, controlling, and coordinating organizations like a public enterprise to achieve the designed objectives in the minimum possible resources at the quickest possible time. Adams and Ebert define strategic management (1985:536) as a "continuous process of thinking through the organization's current mission, thinking through the environmental conditions, and then combining these elements by setting forth a guide for tomorrow's decisions and results."

VI. METHODS OF EFFECTIVE COMMUNICATION

A. *Different Effective Methods of Communication*

Most of the time, when the word communication come to people's minds, they think about exchanging ideas and information using words. Even then, such verbal communication is just a small part of communication. In the 21st century, businesses have access to several communication methods of communication which can be used internally and with external audiences. The main forms of communication that the companies can use include formal business meetings and print to videoconferencing and social media of the new age. Businesses can utilize several tools for addressing audiences who are in locations that are both near and far. While a lot of attention is received by the new methods of effective communication, the value and relevance of traditional communication methods still exist. Thus, several different forms of communication exist, and the determination of the way that is right for the organization is a vital decision that needs to be taken. The conventional methods of communication are oral or verbal by a sender and reading or listening for the receiver. Most of the communication is oral, with one party speaking and others listening. However, there are a number of ways of communication that do not involve spoken or written language directly.

Nonverbal communication (body language) consists of actions, gestures, and other aspects of physical appearance that, combined with facial expressions (such as smiling or frowning), can be powerful means of exchanging messages. At times, a person's body may be "talking" even as they maintain silence. And sometimes, when people speak, their bodies say different things than what their words convey. A *mixed message* occurs when a person's words communicate one message, their bodies or nonverbal aspect communicates something else. Although technologies such as text messages and e-mail have lessened the importance of nonverbal communication, most organizational communication still occurs face-to-face. Every verbal message comes with a nonverbal component. Receivers interpret messages by assuming meaning from everything available. When nonverbal signs are consistent with verbal messages, they act to reassure the messages. But when these nonverbal and verbal messages display inconsistencies, they add to the confusion for the receiver of the message. Management actions are especially significant because subordinates display more confidence in what managers do than what they say. Unless efforts are consistent with the communication, a feeling of distrust will undermine the effectiveness of any future social exchanges.

Oral communication skills: A major part of a manager's day is spent conversing with other managers and employees, the ability to speak and listen become critical to success. For instance, oral communication skills are usually used when a manager makes sales presentations, conducts interviews, performs employee evaluations, and holds press conferences. In general, managers prefer to rely on oral communication because communication tends to be complete and thorough when talking in person. In face-to-face interactions, a person can judge how the other party reacts, get immediate feedback, and answer questions. In general, people tend to assume that talking to someone face-to-face or telephonically are more credible than receiving a written message. Face-to-face communication permits not only the exchange of words but also the opportunity to see nonverbal communication. However, verbal communicating has its drawbacks. It can show inconsistencies unless all parties hear the same message. And although oral communication is helpful in conveying viewpoints of others and providing an openness that encourages people to communicate, it is not considered as a strong tool for implementing a policy or issuing directives in case specifics are involved.

Written communication skills: Written communication has several advantages. First, it provides a handful of records for referrals and follow-ups. Second, written communication is a completely inexpensive means of sharing identical messages to a huge audience. A major limitation of written communication is that the sender lacks information about communication being received unless a reply is required. Unfortunately, writing skills are often difficult to master, and many individuals have problems in writing simple, clear, and direct copies. Believe it or not, poorly written documents cost a lot of money. Just imagine, how

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much can a bad writing cost a company annually? According to a Canadian consulting and training firm, one employee who writes just one poorly worded memo per week over a year can cost a company \$4,258.60. This is why, managers should be able to write clearly. The ability to prepare notes, letters, sales reports, and other written documents may tell the difference between success and failure.

VII. CHARACTERISTICS OF EFFECTIVE COMMUNICATION

In *Effective Public Relations* (1952), University of Wisconsin professor Scott M. Cutlip and Allen H. Center defined a set of principles known today as the 7C's of communication. This list has been widely adopted – with or without slight variations – and is now being considered a staple in public relations studies.

Completeness: Effective communications are complete, i.e., the receiver understands all the information he needs to process the given message to generate action or response. A complete message minimizes the need for follow-up queries and eases the communication process.

Conciseness: Conciseness means keeping your message to the point. This attribute is more about the content of the message rather than the length. Even a short note can include unrequired information. Conciseness helps the receiver to focus on significant part of the message, speeds up information processing, and caters for improved understanding.

Consideration: Effective communication has space to understand the receiver's background and perceptions. If your message hits a nerve or doesn't sound respectful, the emotional reaction of the receiver may affect the understanding of your message. Also, tailoring your message to your target audience – e.g., using argumentation and examples relevant to their experience will make it easier for them to process the content and the context.

Concreteness: A concrete message is specific, tangible, and vivid. Facts and figures add to its enhanced credibility and act as support. It helps the audience to understand a broader picture. Concreteness reduces the risk of misunderstanding, builds trust, and encourages constructive criticism.

Courtesy: Courtesy and consideration complement each other to rule out chances of ineffective communications. Courtesy means respecting the receiver's cultural values, and beliefs while curating a polite and unbiased message.

Clearness: The clear your message is, the easier it becomes for the receiver to decode it according to the original intent. While this sounds obvious, most communication gaps germinate out of a lack of clarity. To deliver a compelling message, you must start with a clear communication goal and authentic thoughts. Clear communication built on exact terminology and concrete words reduces ambiguities and confusion.

Correctness: Correct grammar and syntax are the essence of an effective and credible message. Formal errors affect the clarity of message, trigger ambiguity, and create doubts. They might also harm the overall understanding of the message, which could be a sign or red flag for negligence.

VIII. CONCLUSIONS

Communication might be understood as transfer of facts, information, ideas, suggestions, orders, requests, grievances, etc., from one to another person to impart a comprehensive understanding of the subject matter of communication to the received response from the recipient to such communication. Communication plays a critical role in every organization. Growth and development of businesses depends upon factors like hard-working and dedicated employees, teamwork, proper decision making, etc. All these factors come into effect only with implementation of effective communication in an organization. Generating desired outcomes and attracting bigger clients is possible only when the power of communication between the employees working in the company is harnessed to its true potential.

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